

Photochromic behaviour of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II)-phenolphthalein system

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Potassium hexacyanoferrate(II)-phenolphthalein system gives pink colour on exposure to light and it reverts back in dark. The effect of variation of various parameters like pH, light intensity, concentration of phenolphthalein and concentration of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II), on the rates of forward and backward reactions of this photochromic system has been observed. A tentative mechanism has been proposed.

Photochromism is a light-induced reversible change of colour. It has a variety of applications. Marckwald¹ observed photochromism in solution and in the solid state for the first time, which may be due to intramolecular changes. Photochromic materials are useful in optical information storage, cosmetics, sunglasses, actinometry, military camouflage, photoswitchable biomaterials, etc.² Crystal violet derivatives seem to undergo photoionization with a colour change to blue³. Photochromism in methanol-ethanol solution of triphenylmethane dyes like malachite green and crystal violet was observed by Lifschitz⁴. Photochromism, where photoionization is involved brings noticeable environmental changes from electrically neutral to ionic states (cationic), which may be used for photocontrol of physical properties⁵⁻⁷. Photochromic nature of malachite green was also studied by Tokumara and Loyle⁸. They reported that its photochromic nature is due to its resonating forms. Photochromic behaviour in methylene blue-methanol system has been studied by Vyas *et al.*⁹. Yokoyama *et al.*¹⁰ studied the metal ion complexation and photochromism of triphenylmethane dye derivatives incorporating monoaza-15-crown-5 moieties.

Results and discussion

A graph between $1 + \log(\text{absorbance})$ and time was plotted, which was linear (Fig. 1). After reaching an optimum value, the absorbance remains constant. Thereafter, the light source was cut off. It was observed that the reaction reverts back, which is evident from the decreasing value of absorbance. The plot of $\log(\text{absorbance})$ vs time for this backward reaction was also found to be linear. This behaviour indicates that the forward and backward reactions, both, followed pseudo first order kinetics. The rate constant was determined by the expression

$$k = 2.303 \times \text{slope}$$

Effect of pH :

The effect of pH on generation and disappearance of colour was observed in the pH range 5.5 to 8.0 keeping all other factors identical. The results are shown in Table 1(a).

[Phenolphthalein] = $7.60 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Potassium] hexacyanoferrate = $8.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, intensity of light = 60.0 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 7.0

Fig. 1

Table I

(a) Effect of pH

[Phenolphthalein] = $7.60 \times 10^{-5} M$, [Potassium hexacyanoferrate(II)] = $8.00 \times 10^{-2} M$, intensity of light = 60.0 mW cm^{-2}

pH	$k_f \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$	$k_b \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$
5.5	0.76	1.10
6.0	0.91	1.23
6.5	2.40	1.81
7.0	2.76	1.10
7.5	1.53	1.01
8.0	0.98	0.96

(b) Effect of [Phenolphthalein]

[Potassium hexacyanoferrate] = $8.0 \times 10^{-2} M$, intensity of light = 6.00 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 7.0

[Phenolphthalein] $\times 10^4 M$	$k_f \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$	$k_b \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$
0.56	2.46	1.05
0.66	2.57	1.08
0.76	2.76	1.10
0.86	2.63	1.02
0.96	2.61	0.94
1.06	2.50	0.85
1.16	2.28	0.57
1.26	2.20	0.49
1.36	2.08	0.42
1.46	1.87	0.40
1.56	1.59	0.39

(c) Effect of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II)

[Phenolphthalein] = $7.60 \times 10^{-5} M$, intensity of light = 60.0 mW cm^{-2} , pH = 7

$K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \times 10^2 M$	$k_f \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$	$k_b \times 10^4 (\text{s}^{-1})$
4.00	2.05	0.58
5.00	2.12	0.68
6.00	2.16	0.82
7.00	2.35	0.95
8.00	2.76	1.10
9.00	2.51	0.69
10.00	2.00	0.55

The effect of pH on reaction rate was observed in the pH range 5.5 to 8.0. The rates of the forward and backward reactions both increase with increasing pH. The rate of the reaction reaches a maximum at pH 7.0 but on further increase in pH above 7.0, the reaction rate is retarded. It may be attributed to the fact that the rate of reaction increases above pH 5.5 as the abstraction of proton from phenolphthalein molecule is facile; thus converting it into its quinonoid form while the majority of phenolphthalein molecules will remain in anionic form above pH 7.0. This anionic form will have the little tendency to interact with the photoelectron generated by potassium hexacyanoferrate on exposure.

Effect of concentration of phenolphthalein and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) :

The effect of concentration of phenolphthalein and potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) on the rates of forward and backward reactions of the system was observed and the re-

sults are summarised in Tables I(b) and I(c), respectively.

It is clear from the table that with the increase in phenolphthalein concentration the reaction rate increases due to increase in number of molecules participating in the reaction. But the retardation in the rate of reaction above concentration $7.6 \times 10^{-5} M$ may be due to hinderance caused by phenolphthalein in its own movement towards excited state of potassium hexacyanoferrate in a desired time limit.

It was also observed that the rate of reaction increases on increasing the concentration of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ as more molecules of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ are available for ejection of photoelectron. But a decrease in the rate of reaction was also observed on increasing the concentration of potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) above a particular concentration i.e. $8.00 \times 10^{-2} M$. It may be explained on the basis that potassium hexacyanoferrate(II) solution is pale yellow in colour and its larger concentration will decrease the intensity of light in the bulk in the solution, which in turn will result into retardation of the reaction.

Effect of light intensity :

The effect of intensity of light was observed on this photochromic system. It was observed that the rate of reaction increases on increasing the intensity of light upto 60.0 mW cm^{-2} and thereafter, a decrease was observed on increasing the intensity further. It may be explained on the basis that as the light intensity was increased, the number of photons per unit area also increased, resulting into a higher rate. On the other hand, adverse effect was observed above 60.0 mW cm^{-2} , which may be due to the side thermal reactions.

Mechanism :

On the basis of the observed data, the following tentative mechanism may be proposed for this photochromic system. The primary photochemical ejection of electron from $Fe(CN)_6^{4-}$, and in secondary thermal reaction, the ejected solvated electron abstracts H^+ from phenolphthalein molecule, and phenolphthalein molecule changes into its quinonoid form, which is pink in colour and reaction reverts back in dark.

Experimental

A stock solution of phenolphthalein was prepared by dissolving 0.0318 g in 100.0 ml ethyl alcohol, so that the concentration of indicator solution was $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. A stock solution of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ was prepared by dissolving 21.1100 g in 100.0 ml doubly distilled water, so that the concentration of stock solution was $0.5 M$. 4.0 ml of $0.5 M$ solution of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ was taken and 19.1 ml doubly distilled water and 1.9 ml solution of phenolphthalein was

added to it dropwise. Then the mixture was exposed to light. A 200 W tungsten lamp (Philips; light intensity = 60.0 mW cm⁻²) was used for irradiation purpose. The absorbance of the solution was measured at λ_{max} 550 nm at regular time intervals (using UV-visible spectrophotometer JASCO 7800). It was observed that the solution becomes pink with the passage of time.

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